

INTERFACE CHARACTERISTICS IN FIBRE-REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOY —
MICROSTRUCTURE, MICROMECHANICS AND MANUFACTURE.

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ABSTRACT

The microstructures of some fibre-reinforced aluminium alloys manufactured by liquid metal infiltration are described, with particular reference to the fibre/matrix interface. In the carbon fibre-reinforced alloy, substantial interface reaction takes place to form needle-like carbide crystals extending up to 500nm into the matrix. As a consequence, the matrix is embrittled, the mechanical properties of fibres are degraded, and brittle failure of the composite takes place. In contrast, no interface reaction in the alumina fibre-reinforced aluminium system is observed but a small amount of magnesium segregation at the fibre/matrix interface may have a beneficial effect on metal infiltration and on the quality of the interface bond. In particular, some fibre pull out occurs accompanied by improved composite properties. The Nicalon fibre-reinforced alloy is considered to be an intermediate case. An interface reaction occurs, but the composite shows a mixed mode of failure with some fibre splitting and some interfacial separation.

KEYWORDS: Composites; metal matrix; interface; fibre.

1. INTRODUCTION

The efficiency of fibre reinforcement in a metal matrix is very much dependant upon the quality of the fibre/matrix interface. For example, the interface bond should be sufficiently strong to allow load transfer between fibres via the matrix, yet still permit a measure of fibre pull-out to achieve some degree of composite toughness. These optimum bond strength requirements are, however, difficult to obtain simultaneously in a particular composite.

Thus the crucial role of the interface has long been recognized, as has the importance of its microstructural as well as its mechanical and chemical characteristics. It also follows that any chemical effect between fibre and matrix relating to the method of composite manufacture needs to be taken into account. For example, a low temperature process may require pressures which are sufficiently high to risk mechanically damaging the fibres, whereas the higher temperatures needed to minimize mechanical damage would increase the likelihood of a

chemical reaction at the interface with fibre degradation and local embrittlement of the matrix.

This paper deals with interface stability in aluminium alloys reinforced with a number of ceramic fibres including alumina, carbon and a silicon carbide. The composites were manufactured by liquid metal infiltration of a fibre preform. Interface microstructures have been analysed using analytical scanning and transmission electron microscopy and the data are correlated with fractographic observations on mechanically tested specimens.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The metal matrix consisted of hypoeutectic aluminium containing 7 wt.% silicon and 0.4 wt.% (nominal) magnesium. Reinforcements were alumina (Safimax,* 3 μm diameter), carbon (PAN-based low modulus**, 8 μm diameter) and a SiC-based fibre (Nicalon***, 15 μm diameter); they were all supplied in the form of tows containing several thousand individual fibres in the case of alumina and carbon, and five hundred in the case of Nicalon. The composites were manufactured by liquid metal infiltration of a fibre preform using an applied pressure of < 7MPa and a melt temperature $\sim 750^\circ\text{C}$. The fibres were unidirectionally aligned and fibre volume fractions were ~ 0.4 .

Specimens were cut from the composite plates using a resin-bonded diamond saw and sections prepared for optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) by grinding and then polishing on successively finer grades of diamond abrasive down to 1 μm particle size. Compositional analysis of micro-constituents was performed using an energy-dispersive spectrometer (EDS) attached to the SEM. Additionally, a wavelength-dispersive spectrometer (WDS) system fitted to an electron-probe microanalyser (EPMA) was used to analyse the Nicalon fibres.

Thin (\sim few 100 nm thickness) sections suitable for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were prepared from the composite plate by cutting 3mm diameter discs and mechanically grinding them to a thickness of $\sim 300 \mu\text{m}$. The discs were dimpled on both sides using a VCR model 500 and then thinned by argon ion bombardment in a Gatan Duomill. TEM examination was carried out in a 200 kV microscope fitted with an EDS system.

Fracture surfaces and polished sections through fractures of specimens tested to failure in a four-point bending mode were also examined in the SEM.

3. RESULTS

3.1. The aluminium alloy matrix. All three composite systems studied had a number of common features with regard to the microstructure of the metal matrix. Fig.1a, an optical micrograph taken from a polished transverse section of the Nicalon fibre composite, shows coarse rod-like particles of silicon which tend to grow radially from fibre into matrix. Their three-dimensional nature, often bridging across fibres, is clearly evidenced in the SEM picture, Fig. 1b, taken after deeply etching the sample in a mixed acid solution. In addition,

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intermetallic particles containing a mixture of aluminium, silicon and iron were a fairly common occurrence, the iron in this case being an impurity introduced during manufacture. EDS combined with selected area diffraction (SAD) studies on thin foil specimens in the TEM showed that the intermetallic phase was FeSiAl_5 , a monoclinic structure with lattice parameters of $a = 0.612 \text{ nm}$, $c = 4.144 \text{ nm}$ and $\beta = 91^\circ$. The intermetallic FeSi_2Al_4 , a tetragonal structure with $a = 0.608 \text{ nm}$ and $c = 0.944 \text{ nm}$, was sometimes found adjacent to FeSiAl_5 particles in the alumina fibre reinforced material⁽¹⁾.

All composite systems contained fairly extensive regions of unreinforced matrix separating the fibre tows, often as much as $100 \mu\text{m}$ in width. The efficiency of infiltration, as judged by the population of pores was reasonable, but there were differences between the three composite materials, as we shall mention later.

3.2 Alumina fibre reinforced alloys. The fibres consisted mainly of the tetragonal δ -form of alumina with a fine-grained structure of some 50 nm crystallite size. Compositional analysis using the EDS attachment to the TEM showed that, in addition to aluminium and oxygen, some silicon was present, most likely in the form of silica.

There was a limited amount of porosity present in the composite, especially at interfaces where the fibres were closely spaced. Fig. 2a shows an interface between fibre and aluminium matrix. The interface is not sharply defined and dislocations present in the adjacent aluminium further obscure structural features. SAD analysis did not reveal any new phase at the interface. Using the EDS facility, however, a detectable increase in the magnesium concentration was recorded when the electron beam ($\sim 50 \text{ nm}$ diameter) was positioned on the interface, Fig. 2b, compared with the EDS spectra from fibre, Fig. 2c, and the matrix, Fig. 2d. The fact that the magnesium enrichment coincided with the small silicon signal from the fibre would indicate that the magnesium had diffused into a thin ($< 50 \text{ nm}$) surface layer on the fibre. No such magnesium enrichment was detected at a fibre-silicon interface or at a fibre-intermetallic interface.

The fracture surface of a specimen tested in four-point bending is shown in Fig. 2e, taken from the tensile surface with the bending axis aligned parallel to the fibre direction. Appreciable pull out of the fibres has occurred, the exposed lengths equating with some 10's of fibre diameters. The smooth appearance of the fibre surfaces confirmed that little chemical reaction had taken place between fibre and matrix.

3.3 Carbon fibre reinforced alloy. Infiltration of the carbon fibre preform was not as effective as the alumina preform. In particular, porosity occurred in the outer regions of each fibre tow which was associated with the close packing of fibres.

Fig. 3a is a transmission electron micrograph illustrating an interfacial region between carbon fibre and aluminium metal. A reaction zone is clearly revealed containing rod-like crystals, of width $\sim 20 \text{ nm}$ and length up to 500 nm , which appear to nucleate on the fibre and grow into the matrix in a variety of directions. EDS combined with SAD identified the crystals as Al_4C_3 , a rhombohedral structure with lattice parameters $a = 0.334 \text{ nm}$ and $c = 2.50 \text{ nm}$. All carbide crystals analysed were found to have basal planes oriented parallel to the

longitudinal axis. Where carbon fibres were close together, the carbide crystals sometimes formed a "bridge" between them. The interface structure was quite different where silicon contacted a carbon fibre, Fig. 3b, the interface being well defined with no evidence of any chemical reaction having taken place.

The failure mode of this composite material differed somewhat from that of the Safimax reinforced alloy. The fracture surface exhibited brittle characteristics and a crack, once initiated, tended to spread catastrophically across entire fibre bundles and leave a planar surface with virtually no fibre pullout, Fig. 3c. Where fibres were found to be exposed at the fracture, closer examination showed them to be associated with a region of porosity and poor infiltration around the edges of fibre tows, Fig. 3d.

3.4 Nicalon reinforced aluminium alloy. Generally, the infiltration of the Nicalon fibre prepreg was good, with intimate contact between fibre and matrix being established in most regions of the composite. Only where the fibres were very closely packed was porosity found.

Fig. 4a is a TEM picture taken from an interface region showing a cluster of crystals growing from the fibre surface into the matrix. These were identified, using EDS and SAD, as aluminium carbide. The density of clusters varied considerably along the interfaces. The outermost region of the fibre (depth ~ 100nm) has a different appearance from the rest of the fibre and EDS showed that it contained magnesium and aluminium in approximately equal amounts, Fig.4b. The major elements in the zone were silicon and carbon but there was a slightly higher oxygen concentration compared with the rest of the fibre. SAD gave the same patterns from outer zone and fibre interior, both indicative of microcrystalline β silicon carbide, a tetragonal structure with $a = 0.497$ nm and $c = 0.692$ nm. The outer layer was present regardless of whether aluminium, silicon or an intermetallic phase contacted the fibre at that point. Fig. 4c shows a reaction product growing from the fibre which was identified as aluminium oxide. The crystals in these clusters appear to be slightly larger, on average, than the carbide and to be rather more irregularly shaped. Much of the interface showed, however, no sign at all of a chemical reaction. Another type of second phase located at the fibre/matrix interface, Fig. 4d, was found to be a mixed oxide containing magnesium and aluminium. Such particles occurred only in isolated places on the fibre and closer study of the interface with the fibre suggested that they had not formed by a chemical reaction between matrix and fibre but had been deposited from the melt during the solidification process.

EPMA data obtained on the Nicalon fibre using the WDS facility indicated that the chemical composition of the fibre was ~33 wt.% carbon, ~ 58 wt.% silicon, and ~ 9 wt.% oxygen, all values ± 2 wt.%. Assuming then that the oxygen present is combined with the silicon, either as SiO_2 and/or non-stoichiometric silicon oxycarbide (SiO_xC_y) as suggested by other workers^(2,3), some of the carbon present must exist as free carbon. This proposition was confirmed by studies on the shape of the carbon x-ray peaks, the essential point being that the peak intensity and area is dependant upon the chemical state of the carbon⁽⁴⁾. By comparing the shape of the carbon x-ray peak obtained from the Nicalon fibre with those from pure silicon carbide and amorphous carbon, it was deduced that ~ 15 vol.% of free carbon was present in the fibre. Details of this work will be published elsewhere.

The fracture surfaces of this material exhibited a mixed mode of failure, with some splitting of

the Nicalon fibre indicating substantial fibre/matrix bonding, and also instances of separation at the fibre/matrix interface. A polished section perpendicular to the fracture face, Fig. 4e, shows these features together with crack deflection at the matrix intermetallics.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Microstructure and Manufacturing. The first feature of note is that generally satisfactory infiltration has been achieved for all three composites, although the effectiveness has differed from one system to another. Not surprisingly, a major difficulty arose when fibres were pushed together by the advancing liquid metal front because their penetration was impeded by the constriction of passageways between fibres. The carbon fibre reinforced material appeared most prone to this effect, so much so that the poorly infiltrated edges of fibre tows provided an easy route for the propagation of cracks, as seen in Fig. 3d. The better response to infiltration of the Nicalon reinforced composite is thus to be expected since these filaments are thicker (15µm compared with 8µm diameter for carbon), more rigid, and less likely to be displaced by the pressure of the liquid metal front. The good infiltration of alumina fibres indicates, however, that here some other factor must have influenced the process since these fibres were the thinnest (~ 3µm thick) of the three and might have been expected to suffer the most displacement. This leads to the suggestion that the wettability of the alumina fibres has been improved by the segregation of magnesium to the fibre/matrix interface, Figs. 2a-2d. Indeed, there are several reports which maintain that magnesium in the melt promotes wetting of the alumina fibres and assists the metal infiltration process. Some workers⁽⁵⁾ argued further that, in the case of an Al-4wt.% Mg alloy/matrix, MgAl₂O₄ was formed on the fibre surface, although whilst such a reaction product might encourage the formation of a strong fibre/matrix bond, it does not follow that it is supportive evidence for improved infiltration. Clearly more work is needed before a quantitative relationship can be established between magnesium concentration and efficiency of infiltration of alumina fibre preforms.

Progressing to the metal solidification stage, the observations on the matrix microstructures accord with a sequence whereby primary grains of aluminium first nucleate within the interfibre regions and the silicon concentrated in the surrounding regions subsequently deposits on fibre surfaces. This agrees with the observation that other matrix second-phase particles, such as the iron-rich intermetallic, tend to be found in fibre regions. The aluminium-silicon eutectic structure which characterises unreinforced cast Al-7wt.% Si alloy was not, however, well defined in the composites due to the disturbance caused by the presence of fibres, as has been reported by other workers^(1,5). The size of the primary aluminium grains was reduced and the silicon particles were coarser, the scale of the microstructure reflecting fibre size and fibre spacing in the preform.

Turning to the formation of second phases at the interface, there are substantial differences between the three composite systems. At the temperature of metal infiltration, the carbon fibres reacted the most strongly, to give aluminium carbide according to $4 \text{Al}_{(L)} + 3 \text{C}_{(S)} \rightarrow \text{Al}_4\text{C}_3\text{(S)}$, although no reaction with the silicon constituent of the alloy was observed. The material evidently was at temperature long enough to produce aluminium carbide crystals extending ~ 0.5µm into the matrix.⁽⁶⁾ The alumina fibre composite did not, as mentioned above, appear

to contain any additional phases at the interface. However, the Nicalon reinforced system showed not only evidence of aluminium carbide but also of aluminium oxide. Such growth was not as extensive as the aluminium carbide crystals formed in the carbon fibre system and much of the Nicalon/matrix interface appeared free of any reaction. The morphology of the carbide crystals otherwise paralleled the interface reaction observed in the carbon fibre composite and indicates that the reaction is associated with the free carbon present in the Nicalon fibre. Similar conclusions were reached by Viala et al⁽⁷⁾ in heat treatment studies on mixtures of Nicalon and aluminium. They also pointed out that, at temperatures below ~ 650°C, silicon carbide would not be attacked by aluminium to form carbide, and if silicon was added to the melt the reaction would be inhibited up to much higher temperatures. This is in agreement with studies⁽⁸⁾ on an aluminium alloy composite containing boron fibres coated with a layer (1-2µm thick) of silicon carbide, which showed no evidence of any aluminium carbide reaction. The discovery of alumina crystals at the Nicalon-fibre interface accords with another proposition of Viala, namely that the silica present in the fibre reacts with molten aluminium according to $4 \text{ Al} + 3 \text{ SiO}_2 \rightarrow 2 \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3 + 3 \text{ Si}$, the silicon released readily dissolving in the melt alloy. The fact that the carbide interface reaction in the Nicalon fibre composite is much less than in the carbon fibre composite is hardly unexpected in view of the inhibiting effect of the oxide growth and the need to keep the interface supplied with carbon from sub-surface regions of the fibre. Thus the outward diffusion of elements from the Nicalon fibre is accompanied by an inward flow of aluminium and magnesium from the matrix to produce the diffuse zone seen in outer regions of the fibre. It was not possible to state whether any new phase was associated with this zone although it is feasible that microcrystalline oxides of magnesium and aluminium might be dispersed in the finely crystalline (~ 3 to 7 nm crystallite size) network of β -SiC.

4.2 Microstructure and micromechanics. There can be little doubt that the network of coarse silicon particles in the metal matrix, often bridging fibres to form a three-dimensional network, Fig.1b, will act in such a way as to inhibit plastic flow of metal when the composite is subjected to strain. There is evidence, too, that intermetallic particles may contribute to a reduced matrix ductility and even provide a source of cracks within the composite, Fig.4e. The present observations indicate, nevertheless, that the matrix plays a secondary role with regard to developing the optimum mechanical properties expected of a fibre-reinforced composite, and that the fibre/matrix interface characteristics are the more important in these composite systems. Hence fibre/matrix bond strength and interface sliding are seen to control the strength, the brittleness and the toughness of the composite.

At one extreme of behaviour is the carbon fibre reinforced material in which extensive chemical reaction has occurred at the interface to form long rod-like crystals of aluminium carbide penetrating a significant distance into the aluminium matrix, Fig.3a. This leads to the development of a strong bond between the fibre and the matrix and, in addition, a reduction in ductility of the neighbouring matrix regions and some degradation of the strength of the fibre due to chemical attack. These features combine to produce a material which is extremely brittle such that a crack, once initiated, spreads rapidly across entire fibre bundles to leave the planar fracture surfaces which characterise failure of this material.

In contrast, the alumina fibre reinforced material shows no evidence of a chemical reaction at

fibre/matrix interface. Nevertheless, the strength of the interface bond is sufficient to allow load transfer from fibre to fibre via the matrix and give desirable properties in the transverse direction⁽¹⁾. At the same time some degree of fibre pull out is possible when tensile stressing parallel to the fibre direction to give some measure of fracture toughness.

The behaviour of the Nicalon fibre reinforced material is considered to be an intermediate case. Some interface reaction occurs, to form clusters of aluminium carbide and oxide crystals, but this is less extensive than in the carbon fibre composite and, as a consequence, the material is not as brittle.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Nicalon fibre reinforced composite, prepared section; (a) optical micrograph showing iron-rich intermetallics and coarse silicon phases, (b) scanning electron micrograph after deep etching showing network of silicon and intermetallics.

Figure 2. Alumina reinforced composite; (a) transmission electron micrograph of thin section showing fibre/matrix interface, (b) EDS of interface showing presence of magnesium, (c) EDS of fibre and (d) EDS of matrix; (e) scanning electron micrograph of fracture showing clean fibre surfaces.

a

b

c

d

Figure 3. Carbon fibre reinforced composite; transmission electron micrographs showing (a) carbides at fibre/aluminium interface and (b) absence of reaction at fibre/matrix interface; optical micrographs of polished section showing (c) brittle nature of fibre tows and (d) failure around a fibre tow (marked with arrow).

Figure 4. Nicalon fibre reinforced composite; (a) transmission electron micrograph of thin section showing carbide reaction and diffuse zone at fibre surface, (b) EDS of diffuse zone, (c) as Fig.4a, but showing alumina crystals, (d) as Fig. 4a, but showing deposited mixed oxide phase, (e) scanning electron micrograph of polished section through fracture; note deflection of crack at intermetallic particles.